

Literary idea and theme in "Karakoz Majnun" by Said Ahmad

Bakhriddinov Muslimbek Muhiddinovich

Teacher of the Department of English Language and Literature

Fozilova Mukhlisa Ganisher qizi

First stage student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: *While reading a fiction, the reader tries to analyze the work artistically in order to fully understand its meaning. The role of theme and idea in belles-lettres are so important that the reader can better understand the content of the work by knowing them. Through the analysis of the fiction and information in this article, you will gain more knowledge about the theme and idea, the literary content of the work.*

Keywords — idea, problematic, theme, ideological plan, immortal theme, logical idea, socio-philosophical generalization and figurative form in a fiction.

INTRODUCTION

"Since fiction is anthropology, it means that human life, his experiences, passions, relationships - all his activities are the "beating heart, his blood and soul, his flame and sun" of a work of art" (V. Belinsky). , all colors, paints and tones, all forms of nature and life can be a phenomenon of poetry (literature - h.U)." [4; 63]

In order to analyze literaryfiction, first of all, we need to know what is the theme and idea, and how important is its place in the literary work.

"The writer's (ideological-artistic) understanding of the social characters reflected in the work of art is problematic (Gr. problema - something put forward, isolated from other aspects of life). For example, in "Sudkhor's death", Sadridin describes usury and greed, while in "Kutlug Qon" Oybek exaggerates the self-awareness and struggle for freedom the ideological problem of the novels is embodied." [5; 114]

We know from literature classes at school that Said Ahmed is a "sharp pen" author. All his works have a complex system of events and a social character. The stories created by the writer cover a certain topic in a wide scope and are formed in the expression of various ideas. These creations are works that can attract the reader regardless of the concept of space and time, and can be important for every society.

"Karakoz Majnun" is one of the best stories written by Said Ahmad during the years of independence. ``Mother waits for Borikhan. She remembers him in the morning prayer. Nevertheless, the writer was able to cover several topics in this work. The development of events is easy to understand, but the fate of the characters in it is different." [2] While reading the story, the reader sometimes feels sorry for Saodat mother, and sometimes She is satisfied with Karakoz's loyalty. Sometimes she thinks about Kumri's loneliness and childlessness, and sometimes she thinks that it is better for him to be with his mother.

If we analyze the literary work of Said Ahmed's "Karakoz Majnun", the social character reflected in it is the sense of

humanity and the dignity of a person who renounced his religion for the benefit of the society. The author expressed the purpose of writing the work through the epigraph in the story:

"From the Holy Qur'an:

"Whoever of you turns away from his religion and dies in this disbelief, then their (meritful) deeds will be wasted, and they will be the people of Hell and will remain there forever."

(Surat al-Baqara, verse 217.)

From the hadith:"One of the ten animals that will enter Paradise is the faithful dog of Ashobi Kahf." (Al-jame al-Kabir.)"[1]

From these hadiths, we can see what the story is about, that is, it tells about a devoted creature and a person who has lost his identity.

"The theme was created in the author's experience, shown by life itself, but still remains in the author's imagination without being fully formed, it demands embodiment in images and arouses the desire to work in the author" [5 ; 115]

"The artistic idea of a work is the content-semantic integrity of a writing as a product of emotional experience and development of life by the author. This idea cannot be recreated with the help of other art and logical formulas; it is the entire literary structure of the work, all its formal expressed by the unity and interaction of its components. Traditionally (and in the narrow sense) the idea is distinguished as the main idea, ideological conclusion and "life lesson" arising from the overall understanding of the work. [6; 27]

The "life lesson" in the "Karakoz Majnun" is Borikhon's kindness. For a son, who left his country, converted to another religion without thinking about his mother who gave birth to him and his father who raised him by honest work, someone whose faith is weak is separated from the approval of his mother, the love of his relatives, his respect in front of his country. It is possible to choose the right path for the growing future generation.

"An idea in literature is an idea that exists in a writing. There are many ideas in literature. There are logical ideas and

abstract ideas ... Logical ideas are concepts that are easily conveyed without figurative means, we call them We can perceive with Logical ideas are characteristic of fiction, philosophical and social generalizations, ideas, cause and effect analysis, that is, abstract elements.

But there are also very subtle, almost imperceptible ideas of a literary work. An artistic idea is an idea embodied in figurative form. It lives only figuratively and cannot be expressed in the form of sentences or concepts. The peculiarity of this idea depends on the disclosure of the topic, the worldview of the author, the communication of the images of life through the speech and actions of the characters. It is in combining logical thoughts, images, all important compositional elements. An artistic idea cannot be transformed into a rational idea that can be concretized or described. This type of idea cannot be separated from the image, from the composition." [1; Topic 8]

"Mother and child meeting... It's interesting that during this process, the dog is somehow disturbed, it feels something, so it "snarls incessantly at a stranger". Borikhon looks like a stranger in his mother's arms. Because "he is drunk and It smelled like a candle lit house." At first, the happy mother did not pay attention to this. It is known that her son Bori Khan turned away from Islam, which his ancestors believed in, and accepted another religion. .

For a mother, religion, national-religious values, and patriotism are above all else. That's why he is disappointed with Borikhan, and sends him to nothingness; he will turn his back on the place where he is going." [2]

In the above fragment, the situation of the image is different, dogs by nature know a good person, and when they see a bad person or sense something suspicious, they become intelligent. Through the given passage, the author explains that Borikhon's return will not bring good things through the action of a speechless creature.

"The formation of an artistic idea is a complex creative process. In literature, it is influenced by personal experience, the writer's worldview and understanding of life. The idea can last for several years and decades, and while the author tries to realize it, suffers, looks for suitable means for its implementation. All themes, symbols, all events chosen by the author are necessary to more fully express the main idea, its nuances, shades. However, it should be understood that the artistic idea is not equal to the ideological plan, the plan that often appears not only in the writer's head, but also on paper. Studying non-fictional reality, reading diaries, notebooks, manuscripts, archives, literary scholars reconstruct the history of the idea, the history of creation, but often cannot find the artistic idea. Sometimes the author turns against himself, surrendering to the original idea for the sake of artistic truth, inner idea." [2; 99]

The choice of the topic depends on the author's worldview, attitude to social events, mind, worldview, culture, professional skills, way of thinking, civic consciousness, moral and aesthetic beliefs, philosophical and legal views, ideological-political and other positions.

"Immortal themes" is a living memory of human morality, human relations, a memory that humanity establishes in the images of art.

"Immortal themes" in a fiction pass from one era to another and embody the most generalized and stable features of human character in the course of historical development.

This story by Saeed Ahmed is one of those timeless themes. Of course, the question "why?" is natural. The creature depicted in the story and its loyalty to its owner is an all-time occurrence, a theme that always comes up in our society.

The writer lovingly described it as "small, with two belt-like stripes on its back - one black and one brown", "its beak and two eyes are black, one eye is blunt above If you have noticed, from the beginning to the end of the story, the writer describes Saodat as a constant companion , when the old son is immersed in thought, she calms down as if thinking. Even though she misses the old son, Borikhon is more alien to Saodat than the dog." []

In the story, after the death of the old woman Saodat, the writer draws two drops of tears on her black eyes with a sharp pen in order to convey the spirit of Karakoz to the readers. The death of the Karakoz madman at the end of the story saddens the reader.

Humans have always been interested in the themselves and the manifestation of their character in one or another situation. In the fiction, as in life, a person encounters duty, honor, conscience, dust, sin, heroism, patriotism, jealousy, envy, slander, betrayal, revenge, freedom and many other eternal concepts.

Reflecting on the heroes of the work, sympathizing with them, the audience's soul, mind and heart seem to have internal moral qualities, self-esteem, self-formation, improvement.

In conclusion, the story contains a lot of meaning. The value of Uzbek traditions is emphasized by showing the actions of an unworthy child. It is true that the loyalty of a dog is always more glorious than the destruction of a mother's heart by a son.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ulug'ov. Theory of literary studies. Instructional manual. Tashkent. 2016.
- [2] B. Karimov. Methodology of literary studies. Instructional manual for philologists. Tashkent. 2011.
- [3] D. Kuronov. Literature, etc. about(collection of articles). Tashkent. "Academic edition". 2019.
- [4] D. Kuronov. Introduction to literary studies. T: Publishing House of Folk Heritage named after A. Qadiri. 2004.
- [5] H. Umurov. Literary theory: a guide for higher educational institutions. T: Publishing House of Folk Heritage named after A. Qadiri. 2004-264. p.
- [6] L. Tashmuhamedova. Literary history and theory: textbook. Tashkent: Shafoat Nur Faiz, 2020.160b.
- [7] T. Boboyev. Basics of literary studies. Tashkent. T: "Uzbekistan". 2002